

DESIGN OF MOULDS FOR THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE COMPONENTS USING A C.A.D PACKAGE

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ABSTRACT

In the moulding of fibre reinforced laminates, distortions are produced in the moulded part as it cools. These distortions are thermally induced as a consequence of the anisotropy of the laminate. A geometric modelling technique is used to generate a surface for a finite element model. Assumed fibre orientations are included in the finite element model and a thermal stress analysis is used to predict the distortions due to the cooling of the part. This process can be repeated until the desired dimensions of the part are achieved. A mould can now be designed which will allow close tolerance parts to be manufactured.

Keywords : Mould design, thermoplastic composites, finite element analysis, thermal stresses.

1. INTRODUCTION

Thermal stresses are recognised as features arising during the manufacture of conventional thermosetting composites[1], however the high temperature at which advanced thermoplastics composites must be processed suggests an increased significance of thermally induced distortions and stresses in a finished component fabricated with this new class of composite[2]. Whereas experience indicates that the internal stresses do not detract from the advantages of these materials[3], it is well known that when a thermoplastic fibre-reinforced laminate is formed in a mould at a temperature above the melting point, cooled and removed from the mould, it assumes a shape which can be significantly different from the shape of the mould.

This phenomenon is known as the spring forward effect and it is observed as a decrease in enclosed angle of a formed part. Therefore if a composite right angled component is formed on a right angled mould, the right angle will reduce in the finished part [4]. This effect is a result of the anisotropy of thermal properties of the composite material, specifically the large difference between in-plane and out-of-plane thermal expansion coefficients. Figure 1 shows the room temperature coefficients of thermal expansion for APC-2. One method of predicting the spring forward effect for complex shaped components is through the use of finite element analysis.

This paper will deal with the use of finite element analysis for the design of tools for diaphragm forming thermoplastic composites and the technique will be demonstrated using the elliptical dish mould shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1 Room Temperature Coefficients of Thermal Expansion for APC-2

Figure 2 Photo of Elliptical Dish Mould

2. FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

2.1 Mesh Generation

Due to the limitations of the mesh generation package available a geometric modelling technique has been employed to generate the grids for the finite element model. The surfaces are described using Bezier curves with each different type of surface being generated by a different subprogram. The surfaces are described by parametric representation and the input data file contains the control points used to describe the different surfaces, the number of parametric lines in the u-direction, the number of parametric lines in the v-direction and the number of surface points to be evaluated along the parametric lines. The x,y,z co-ordinates of surface points are located along the u-parametric and the v-parametric lines.

Figure 3 Geometry of Elliptical Dish Section

The elliptical dish shown in Figure 3 consists of five surfaces so five sub-programs were developed. The x,y,and z-coordinates of each grid were stored in a file and then read into the finite element preprocessor and used for mesh generation of the finite element model.

2.2 Model type

There are two classical approaches to the finite element analysis of composite systems. They differ in their underlying descriptions of the layered system i.e. discrete or composite. In a discrete analysis the inhomogenous nature of the system is modelled so that all material interfaces fall along element boundaries (thus each element contains only one type of material). Because of the complicated nature of the layer interaction, in general, very fine grids are required.

An alternative to a discrete representation is to model the layered system as an equivalent homogenous, orthotropic continuum material. Because the detailed geometry of the layering is not represented, coarse grids may be used. The advantage of a discrete analysis is that the local stress and strain states at and near the layer interfaces and at the edges of the laminate are directly calculated while the main disadvantage is the excessive computational cost required for the analysis of two and three dimensional systems with large numbers of layers. The advantage of a composite analysis is the low computational cost. The model presented in this paper is of the "composite analysis" type and the finite element package employed was ABAQUS [5]. Previous research has shown this analysis to be practical for modelling thermally induced stresses in thermoplastic composites[6].

2.3 Model Assumptions

The purpose of the model is to determine the deformations in a laminate resulting from the thermal strains set up during the cooling of the laminate from its processing temperature (380°C) to room temperature (20°C). The model was constructed subject to the following assumptions.

- (1) The material layers behave macroscopically.
- (2) Kirchoff plate bending theory is assumed.
- (3) Stress free temperature assumed to be 343°C.
- (4) Material behaves orthotropically.
- (5) No temperature gradients across laminates.
- (6) The effect of the diaphragms on the laminate is assumed to be negligible.
- (7) The cooling rate is assumed to be in the range of 10-700°C/min.
- (8) Material properties are temperature dependent.

2.4 Element Data

The laminates were modelled using 8 node, reduced integration, doubly curved shell stress/displacement elements with five and six degrees of freedom per node. Each lamina of the laminate is input on a separate data card specifying its thickness, orientation relative to the local axis

and the number of integration points through the thickness of the lamina, proceeding in the normal direction. Material properties are input for each named lamina within the laminate. As we are dealing with only one material type in this analysis the only variation in material properties occurs when the orientation of the fibres in individual laminae vary with respect to the other layers. The material properties are input as functions of temperature and the program interpolates linearly for the values between those given.

The orientation of each of the plies in the laminate is provided by a subroutine. This subroutine is called at each material (constitutive) calculation point and the user must code the direction cosines giving the preferred orientation in which orthotropic material properties have been defined in terms of the normal (non-oriented) basis directions. The normal material basis directions are surface coordinates for shell elements.

2.5 Analysis Type

A static analysis is carried out for the non-linear analysis in the finite element step. Automatic incrementation is used to divide the step into a number of increments during which the temperatures are changed gradually. The time scale used in the static analysis is a natural one, i.e. the total time interval is given in seconds with increments varying according to the convergence rate of the solution. The convergence rate of the solution is determined by the force and moment tolerances which are specified at the beginning of the static analysis. Displacements are calculated at each increment and summed over the total number of increments in the step.

2.6 Boundary Conditions

The dimensions of the part model were taken from the surface generation program and the fixed boundary conditions of the model are depicted in Figure 4.

1. No displacements in y-direction along dashed line parallel to x-axis.
2. No displacements in x-direction along dashed line parallel to y-axis.
3. No displacements in x or y-directions in shaded areas.
4. No displacements in z-direction along heavy line.

Figure 4. Fixed Boundary Conditions on Finite Element Model

In order to find the fibre orientations, a part was formed of the required geometry and the fibre alignment was approximated. A quarter section was used to model the component as it is symmetric about the x and y axis. The parts modelled were $(0/90)_{2S}$, $(0/90)_{4S}$, $(-45/90/45/0)_S$, $(-45/90/45/0)_{2S}$ and the results are presented Section 3.3.

3. MOULD DESIGN AND EXPERIMENTAL WORK

3.1 Mould Design

In order to validate the finite element analysis an elliptical dish mould was designed and manufactured. The mould was male in nature and was made from stainless steel. The mould was designed as shown in Figure 7 with a convex curvature and a central deflection of 0.6mm. This height was chosen based on experimental results from previous work[7] for a similar shaped component. A photo of the mould is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 7. Central Deflection on Mould

3.2 Experimental Work

A number of 8-ply and 16-ply elliptical dish parts were diaphragm formed from APC-2 in the autoclave. Processing conditions for all parts were 380°C with a consolidation pressure of 750kPa. A photo of a (0/90)_{2S} part is shown in Figure 8(a). A quarter section was cut from one (0/90)_{4S} part to measure the thickness variation, a photo of this cross section can be seen in Figure 8(b). The thickness measured was 2.14 mm at the center and this varied by +/-15% along the part. Each part was measured for deflection along its major axis. The deflections in the parts are compared to the predicted results in Figure 9 and Figure 10.

(a)

(b)

Figure 8. Photos of (a) (0/90)_{2S} Elliptical Dish Part and (b) Cross Section of (0/90)_{4S} Part.

3.3 Results

The analysis predicted positive deflections in the z-direction on the flat part of the dish and plots of the predicted and experimental results versus are shown in Figure 9 and Figure 10, where a is half the major axis of the ellipse and x is the position of the node along the x-axis, as shown in Figure 7.

(a)

(b)

Figure 9. Plots of Predicted and Experimental Deflections for (a) $(0/90)_{2S}$ and (b) $(0/90)_{4S}$ Layup.

(a)

(b)

Figure 10. Plots of Predicted and Experimental Deflections for (a) $(-45/90/0/45)_S$ and (b) $(-45/90/0/45)_{4S}$ Layup.

From these results it can be seen that the finite element analysis has useful predictive capabilities for post moulding distortion. The predicted results for the $(0/90)_{2S}$ and $(0/90)_{4S}$ layups were very accurate giving the same values for central deflections as measured in the diaphragm formed component. The maximum variation along the major axis between experimental and predicted deflection was 0.25mm. The results for the $(-45/90/45/0)_S$ and $(-45/90/45/0)_{2S}$ were not as accurate with their central deflections differing by 0.2mm. The parts formed using $(-45/90/45/0)$ layups exhibited buckling of the fibres. This effect wasn't analysed in the finite element analysis and could account for some error. From the experimental work on the elliptical dish part, it was found that the side of the part also distorted. This distortion was not evident in experimental work carried out with a cylindrical dish part. This could be due to the non axisymmetry of the elliptical dish and could also explain some of the difference.

Work by J. A Nairn et al [3] has shown that some of the assumptions may lead to inaccuracies particularly the assumption of zero thermal gradient through the thickness. This may lead to errors as the part thickness and cooling rate increases.

A unidirectional composite material undergoes inplane shear deformation when forced to conform to a surface having compound curvature. This deformation, coupled with the kinematics of mapping paths from a flat surface onto a curved surface, make the prediction of fibre paths nontrivial. The mechanical properties, such as strength and stiffness, and their principal directions vary from point to point in the finished product, being dependent on the local fibre directions. Certain other material properties are also a function of fibre direction, such as thermal expansion and thermal conductivity.

An infinite number of draped fibre configurations are possible for any surface. A method of determining a unique draped configuration is essential to determine fibre paths. The manner in which a surface is draped may lead to the formation of wrinkles or bridging in a part, therefore an understanding of the draping process and the ability to control it are important in determining and controlling fibre paths and continuity and hence the mechanical properties in a formed composite. Much work has been done on the draping of fibres[8],[9],[10] and at present work is being done on the draping of the fibers on the elliptical dish mould so that orientations from a draping simulation may be included in the finite element model. This will increase the accuracy of the model.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A geometric modelling technique has successfully been used as a precursor for mesh generation in a finite element analysis. Finite element analysis has good predictive capabilities for post moulding distortion of complex curvature thermoplastic composite components. Future work should include orientations from a draping simulation and temperature gradients in the finite element model. Moulds for diaphragm forming thermoplastic composites can successfully be designed with the use of finite element analysis.

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